

Quality-Informed Process Mining: A Case for Structured Data Quality Annotations

This document provides detailed experiment results related to the manuscript Quality-Informed Process Mining: A Case for Structured Data Quality Annotations submitted to ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data.

Detailed Experiment Results

1. Synthetic Log (Inaccurate Timestamps)

Create recommendation

Commit file for approval

Register approval

Register refusal

Prepare decision report

Send decision report

2. Synthetic Log (Imprecise Timestamps)

3. Synthetic Log (Imprecise and Inaccurate Timestamps)

Conduct sampled check

Send decision report

Register approval

Register refusal

Prepare decision report

Commit file for approval

Create recommendation

Register issues

4. BPIC 2012- W activities (Inaccurate Timestamps)

5. BPIC 2012 W-Activities (Imprecise Timestamps)

6. BPIC 2012- W activities (Imprecise and Inaccurate Timestamps)

7. BPIC 2017- Offer log (Inaccurate Timestamp)

8. BPIC 2017 – Offer Log (Imprecise Timestamp)

9. BPIC 2017- Offer log (Inaccurate and Imprecise Timestamps)

10. BPIC 2018 – Control Summary (Inaccurate Timestamp)

11. BPIC 2018- Control Summary (Imprecise Timestamp)

12. BPIC 2018- Control Summary (Inaccurate and Imprecise Timestamps)

